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IMPACT OF EDUCATIONAL POLICIES ON EDUCATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

The basic and foremost purpose of this study is to analyze the impact of educational policies on education and the development of Pakistan. The independent variables like GDP, net enrollment rate, gross enrollment rate, literacy rate, reserves for education, and HDI are used to analyze the level of development of the education sector and education is used as a dependent variable in this paper. The data was gathered from the World Bank, Ministry of Education, Statistical Bureau of Pakistan and Human Development Report. The study found that low educational budget, child labor, insufficient teachers and lack of modern teaching skills in teachers, provincial conflicts which cause unequal education and the poor and ineffective government policies are the important causes of poor education and development of Pakistan.

Keywords: Development, Education, Literacy, Pakistan

JEL Codes: O38, Z00, Z10, Z18

1. INTRODUCTION

The success of any nation depends upon the development of the education sector. The illiteracy and unemployment are ultimately reduced in the nation when education is promoted. (Ashraf and Ismat, 2016). The United States is on number 1 in education ranking in 2020 and its employment rate is 59.8%. The United Kingdom is on 2nd number in education ranking in 2020 and its employment rate is 75.2%. Canada is on number 3rd in education ranking in 2020 and its unemployment rate is 5.67% only. Germany is on 4th number in education ranking in

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2020 and its employment rate is 77% (World Bank, 2020). Education acts as a backbone for the progress and prosperity of any nation, skills of youth lead any country towards progress and especially vocational skilled youth make progress by leaps and bounds (Khan, 2010).

Pakistan's education sector is managed by the provincial government and ministry of education, while the federal government assists in its curriculum financing. According to an economic survey of 2020, the current population of Pakistan is 216.6 million and the literacy rate for adults increased to 60% and Pakistan is ranked 164th in the education sector (Economic Survey, 2020). Pakistan's population is growing rapidly and it is ranked on six's number in the world's most populous country (Ashraf, Ali, Schultz and Ali, 2013). The Constitution of Pakistan compels free and basic education to the people aged 5 to 16 years old in Article 25-B (Ashraf, Ali, and Hossain, 2013). Its system is divided into 5 different levels; Primary level is from class 1 to 5, classes 6 to 8 are called middle-level classes, High level consists of classes from 9 to 10 leading secondary school certificates, Intermediate level consists of classes 11 and 12 leading higher secondary certificates and for graduation and master degree university programs have been launched. The government started a countrywide action in (NEO) National Educational Policy 1998- 2010, the purpose of which is to gain literacy and fundamental educational amelioration, 2017 education ministry hopes to get 100% enrolment for the students of primary grade. Because of the data and statistics like starting school age, literacy and numeracy skills, etc., one can neither analyze the primary's education effect on literacy nor determine the potential experience. It is the main reason that existing Pakistan literature is lack for approximating actual differences between male and female, ruler & urban, rich and the poor (Government of the Punjab, 2012). To optimize literacy up to 80% among people of age 10 plus, the education sector has initiated new strategies and policies in 2018.

Pakistan's Government is being assisted by the various local and foreign agencies for the betterment of the education system and to provide youngsters with various vocational and educational jobs (Ahmad, Rehman, Ali, Khan and Khan, 2014). The government under Imran Khan has announced the EHSAS scholarship scheme in 2021 for free and effective education at the intermediate level and university level. New projects are initiated to employ fresh graduates as the developed countries in the world provide hourly basis employment to students or undergraduates to consume their extra time for getting experience and becoming independent (Ehsas Scholarship Pakistan, 2020)

This paper aims to look at the strategies and policies that the government of Pakistan implemented with the help of past data and its scanning and conceptualization with the new world. It inscribed the reasons for Pakistan's illiteracy and overthrew the blemishes and weaknesses of the previous work. For the improvement and good performance of the education system, it is vital to conceptualize the prevailing problems and to propose effective measures, which would be workable enough to make vital changes for the good performance of the education system. The enrolment rate of Pakistan remained below 60% till 2017 therefore governmental educational policies and stakeholders could not be able to provide desired results.

Federal Ministry of Education (2019) exposed that the literacy rate for secondary education is 10,884,400 and for post-secondary education, the literacy rate is 3,949,000 which is much better as compared to the past years. This paper would help the researcher in the quantitative assessment of educational level in Pakistan. Educational policies of past Governments have been extensively discussed in this paper, which would assist the researchers to analyze the past data.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

There are numerous studies available that have discussed and focused on illiteracy and poor government educational policies in literature (Memon, 2007; Ahsan, 2003; Samina and Courtney, 2011; Ashraf and Ismat, 2016). Many policies were launched in recent few years but those policies could not be able to provide efficient results to reduce illiteracy and in improvement and development of Pakistan. Samina et al, (2011) stated that there is a huge contradiction in policies that the government launched and steps to achieve its results. Due to poor monitoring and inappropriate management, the applied policies did not give desired results (Ali and Tahir, 2009). Many other causes could not help to achieve 100% enrolment of children in schools (Memon, 2007). One of them is poverty which affects children's minds and ability to gain knowledge because the government could not make appropriate policies to educate lower class people, especially children. Children who belong to poor class families are in a harmed position because of their family environment and their attitude towards education (Mazhar, 2011). Expensive private institutions are also causing a big threat in achieving educational development because parents only try to send their children to private schools due to poor and unequal educational policies of the government (Rehman and Khan, 2011). Up to 2019 net primary enrolment in private and public schools is 73.3% while the targeted ratio was 77% and its Gross Enrolment Rate (GER) is 95.36%.

Pakistan's Educational expenditures have lied between 2.9% as the percentage of GDP, even with a very little amount of this, the rate of utilization has remained at an average of about 90% till 2020. There has been only minor improvement and progress to achieve literacy rate since 2009 - 2010 in Pakistan. For persons aged 10 years and up to it, the rate of illiteracy grown up from 35% to 59.13% till 2017 while the development rate remained motionless or stagnated during this (Country report of Pakistan, 2017). Federal Ministry of Education during 2019 revealed literacy rate which is 60% out of which 71% is Of male and 49% is of female.

Shah, (2003) stated that education performs an important role in progress, prosperity development in rapidly increasing modern world which would become a global village in few coming years, where skills, efficiency, and human capital are important factors to compete with the fast-growing world for the achievement of country's development. Hanif and Arshad, (2016) education would help people to achieve all these goals. To achieve these goals there is a need for a special budget for education as well as the specialized and skilled policymakers.

There is a lack of quality in education and competent teachers, especially at the primary level. Teachers are not well trained, and this causes mind distraction for students. Teachers

should be trained so that they might be able to handle students according to their intellectual level (Ashraf et al, 2013).

3. METHODOLOGY

This is a descriptive study in which past government educational policies are compared with the current government policies and its results are evaluated through given data. In this paper education is a dependent variable that is affected by many independent variables like Net Enrolment rate, Net National Income, GDP and HDI. In this study, the data have been gathered from the World Bank, Ministry of Education, Statistical Bureau and Human Development Report.

4. FINDINGS

Table 1 shows that the literacy rate in 1981 was 25.73% only which was very poor and it increased as the year passes. Eventually, in the recent century especially in the last 10 years, Pakistan improved its literacy rate to a level, in 2017 its rate increased to 2.15% as compared to recent years and in the year 2018 the rate increased to 5.87% but according to the recent survey, the literacy rate decreased by 0.87% in 2019.

While similar country ranking is given below in 2019.

Table 1. Pakistan Literacy Rate-Historical data

Year	Literacy rate%	Annual Changes%
2019	70	5
2018	65	5.87
2017	59.13	2.15
2016	58	1.02
2014	56.98	1.38
2013	55.60	-1.17
2012	56.76	2.03
2011	54.74	-0.64
2010	55.38	0.48
2009	54.89	-0.63
2008	55.53	3.39
2007	52.14	-2.01
2006	54.15	4.28
2005	49.87	7.17
1998	42.70	16.97
1981	25.73	16.97

Data Source: World Bank, (2019)

As compared to a few counties Pakistan's Literacy Rate is much lower even these countries are not well developed but they are focusing to reduce illiteracy. Pakistan is also trying to achieve the

literacy rate to the maximum level. In the coming few years, it would be possible for Government to achieve a maximum literacy rate.

Table 2. Country Ranking in literacy Rate (2019)

Country	Georgia	Sri Lanka	EI Salvador	Bangladesh	Egypt	Bhutan	Pakistan
Literacy Rate%	99.36	91.01	88.48	72.89	71.17	66.56	59.13

Data Source: World Bank, (2019)

- Pakistan stands at 152 out of 189 countries in the United Nation Development Program (UNDP) according to the survey of the Human Development Report in 2019.
- Pakistan's literacy rate is 57% which is good enough when it is compared with neighboring countries but Primary School fell rate is 22.7% which is at a dangerous level.

For the age of 6 to 10 years excluding kindergarten, the Gross Enrolment Rate (GER) at a primary level during 2018-19 as compared to 2015-16 is persisted at 87%.

Table 3. Government Reserve for Education (as % of GDP) of previous 4 Years (Billion)

Year	Pre-primary & Primary education	Secondary Education	Administration
2020_2021	2.931	7.349	1.237
2019_2020	2.83	6.718	1.407

Data Source: Education budget of Pakistan, (2020)

Gross Enrolment Rate in Punjab increased in 2019, in Sindh it remained unchanged, in KPK it fell by 1% and in Baluchistan, it increased by 1% but its literacy rate is much lower than other provinces, there may be many reasons for it.

Table 4. Gross Enrolment Rate (GRN) Province Wise in Last 4 Years

Years	Punjab %	Sindh %	KPK %	Baluchistan %
2015-2016	93	78	88	59
2018-2019	95	78	89	57

Net Enrolment Rate (NER) Province Wise in Last 4 Years

Years	Punjab %	Sindh %	KPK %	Baluchistan %
2015-2016	71	56	67	40
2018-2019	73	58	66	40

Net Enrolment Rate by 2019 in Punjab decreased by 2%, in Sindh it is also decreased by 2% but in KPK it increased by 1% and in Baluchistan NER remained constant in 2019 but its rate is much lower than other provinces of Pakistan.

Table 5. Pakistan’s HDI Trends Based on Consistent Time Series Data and New Goalposts

	Life expectancy at birth	Expected years of schooling	Mean years of schooling	GNI per capita (2017PPP\$)	HDI value
1990	60.1	4.6	2.3	3,049	0.402
1995	61.5	5.0	2.8	3,206	0.426
2000	62.8	5.4	3.3	3,208	0.447
2005	64.0	5.7	4.5	3,780	0.486
2010	65.3	6.8	4.7	4,054	0.512
2015	66.6	7.3	5.1	4,534	0.536
2016	66.8	7.6	5.1	4,6791	0.542
2017	66.9	8.0	5.1	4,821	0.550
2018	67.1	7.9	5.2	4,992	0.552
2019	67.3	8.3	5.2	5,005	0.557

Pakistan falls in the medium human development category with a value of 0.577 according to the Human Development Report (2019) and it stands at 154 out of 189 countries. Pakistan’s progress in each of the indicators of HDI is reviewed in this table. Pakistan's expectancy birth rate boomed by 7.2 years between 1990 and 2019, expected year of schooling and mean year of schooling increased by 3.7 years and 2.9 years and about 64.1% increase in Pakistan’s GNI per capita was observed during the period 1990 and 2019. (Human Development Report, 2019)

According to 2019, Pakistan’s GDP growth rate was about 0.99% and about a 4.85% decline from 2018 (Pakistan Growth Rate historical data 2019). There are only 39% girls and 61% of the total students are boys. At the high school level, overall enrollment decreases sharply. Rural areas are highly affected by the gender ratio, a very disproportionate gender ratio is analyzed in rural high schools, there are 72% of enrolled students boys and only 28% are girls. In private high school, 632259 students are enrolled. Currently, with an estimate of 22.8 million, Pakistan has the world’s second-highest ratio of Out Of School Children (OOSC) aged 5-16 who are not attending school and it represents 44% of the total population in this age group. There are about 5 million children which are not enrolled in school after primary school age in the 5-9 age group. This number of OOSC doubles when with 11.4 million adolescents not receiving formal education between the age of 10-14. Socio-economic status and geography are vital when disparities based on gender; there are about 52% of the poor class children (58% girls) are out of school in Sindh and Baluchistan, there are about 78% of the girls who are out of school. Currently, at the primary level, there are about 8.6 million girls and 10.7 million boys are enrolled. At the lower secondary level this decrease to 2.6 million girls and 3.6 million boys (UNICEF Pakistan, 2019).

5. CONCLUSION

The primary purpose of the paper is to examine the impact and effect of educational policies on the education and development of Pakistan. The study concluded that education plays a function or root in social and economic development. The study also concluded that education in Pakistan is in declined position even though the government has stated forceful measures to boost and elevate the quality and the quantity of its education. It is essential to increase the education budget and to bring betterment in the education skeleton and bring reforms according to the newly developing world. Teachers should be trained enough so they could understand the generation's expectations related to their learning process. New challenges are being faced now by the Pakistan government. It needs more development to compete with other developed countries in the world. For stimulation of progress and to guarantee the equal and standard quality of education. To minimize the significant number of OOSC at all levels of education, UNICEF must help Pakistan's government

In the past decades, Pakistan's education system was not performing well, there are many reasons for it including; lack of monitoring and inspection, insufficient budget, lack of modern teaching skills among the teachers, provincial conflicts and unequal education standards between the private and public sectors, but in recent few years ago, Pakistan's education sector is making progress. The government of Pakistan is giving attention to Early Childhood Education (ECE) for the better improvement of school readiness, nurturing of standard, qualified and equitable Alternative Learning Pathways (ALP) at the basic education level and the growth of school community linkage is also important to optimize on-time enrollment, to minimize drop-out and to ensure completion and transition for all the students. For the improvement of the provincial sector at the system level; government must assist and contribute to the budgeting and planning, effectiveness of data, gauging system. Strict policies must be designed by the government and a special task force must be made to ensure the application of strategies and policies. Girls' education is also as important as men's education that's why a separate system for women's education must be designed according to the cultural and ethical requirements of Pakistan. Special scholarships must be given to needy students so that their poverty may not waste their talent. Jobs are also a giant issue in underdeveloped countries, when fresh graduates do not find a reasonable job, they lose track. Where jobs are important also their industrial revolution is also very important. The young generation must be provided with a platform for the best use of their skills. Equal education must be promoted in all provinces. The syllabus must be the same for private schools and government schools this step would bring a lot of betterment in education and society as well.

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